

THE SIGNIFICANCE AND POSITION OF TEACHING METHODS IN PROFESSIONAL TRAINING

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Abstract: the article focuses on examining the significance and position of instructional techniques within professional education. It explores diverse approaches to defining these techniques, the practical conditions for their utilization, and emphasizes fundamental principles for categorizing them. Based on the conducted research, the author concludes that the teacher plays a pivotal role in shaping the practical content of teaching methods. The article is intended for educators at both school and university levels, as well as for adjuncts and graduate students.

Keywords: methodology, pedagogy, instructor, educational methodology, application criteria, categorization of teaching techniques, instructional technique requirements, practical implementation of teaching methods.

Introduction

Modern realities require constant improvement from the educational process. In society today there is a large-scale change in value priorities, including in the system of professional training. Changes occurring in the learning process, aimed at increasing effectiveness and quality, largely, and more often completely depend on the activation of the cognitive activity of the students themselves.

To stimulate the cognitive activity of students, it is necessary to create the following conditions:

- at the state level (increasing the prestige of education);
- at the ministry level (constant adjustment of the list of competencies for implementation in the educational process);
- at the level of the educational institution (adjustment of curricula);
- one of the key levels of education is the level of preparation and conduct of classes by the teacher, which includes not only highly professional training in the subject, but also the quality of the teacher's training in such disciplines as pedagogy and teaching methods.

It is at the level of conducting classes that the teacher should create conditions for a stimulation of students' cognitive activity using methods and

techniques at the level of both specific and general theoretical methods, using traditional and developmental educational technologies [7]. The level of general methodology presupposes deep knowledge of pedagogy, psychology and teaching methods, which will become the basis for the formation of the level of private methodology. At the level of a private methodology, the teacher finds ways and means to improve the results of the quality of teaching and increase students' interest in the subject of study [4].

Description of the study

Professional training at any stage is designed to fulfill and realize clearly defined goals. At the same time, just like in any production, there is a list of so-called "tools of labor" or means, that is, with the help of which the set goals are achieved. It is also undeniable that the quality of the teacher's tools directly determines the result of the work, in our case this is the quality and result of teaching.

The method in pedagogical activity is the means by which the teacher implements competencies and achieves set goals and objectives both in the holistic pedagogical process, during professional training, and in a specific lesson. Methods of practice-oriented training are of particular importance in modern conditions, when interdisciplinary knowledge and flexibility of skills are becoming a leading trend in the educational process [11]. Method in pedagogical science means a certain direction of work, a certain way of activity of a specialist in the teaching process, this is the path of the teacher's movement towards the goal.

Teaching methods are a list of a number of methods that are revealed and implemented under the condition of joint integrated pedagogical activities of teachers to achieve their goals and objectives in the learning process. At the same time, methods may differ in the degree of joint integrated work of the teacher and students. Today in pedagogy there are more than two hundred interpretations of the concept "method". Translated from Greek, "method" means "way". So, for example, P.F. Kapterev at the beginning of the 20th century considered "a method as a way of teaching in which a strong and rapid assimilation of knowledge occurs." At the same time, the author divides the methods "into the scientific method and the method of presentation" [5]. According to E.G. Skibitsky, I.E. Tolstova and V.G. Shefel, "a teaching method is a historical category and is characterized by three features: the designation of the purpose of learning, the method of assimilation and the nature of the emotional-intellectual interaction of the subjects of learning" [9].

In turn, the authors G.M. Kojaspirova and A.Yu. Kodzhaspirov believe that a method is a set of relatively homogeneous techniques, operations of practical or theoretical mastery of reality, subordinated to solving a specific problem [6]. All authors consider the “method” as a certain path, direction of the teacher’s work and a reciprocal movement towards students in comprehending the material of the discipline. We must identify for ourselves certain reference points in the teaching method that will help in the classification and further application of teaching methods in the classroom:

- the method reflects both the professional achievements of the teacher and the personal qualities of the teacher as a person;
- the level of practical application of the teacher’s method depends on the level of culture and worldview of the teacher [3];
- the method also reflects the level of training of students, while considering not only the layer of knowledge, but also the overall level of students’ worldview, including the psychological development of students;
- the method is designed to always reflect the image educational, developmental, educational goals and objectives of a certain stage of training;

- teaching methods are expressed in a variety of ways for students to master educational material;
- teaching methods are also revealed in the ways of conveying the material to students directly by the teacher himself with the help of teaching aids, methodological techniques and pedagogical technologies;
- disclosure of the teaching method is realized through feedback between students and the teacher, including the quality and outcome of training;
- undoubtedly, when using teaching methods, it is necessary to take into account the specific conditions in educational institutions and in each individual lesson;
- no matter what innovative teaching technologies are used in education, the basic teaching methods (verbal, practical, visual) are always used in the educational process, while the name may be modified or various classifications of teaching methods may be expanded.

As mentioned earlier, there is a general methodology (theoretical, basic, generally accepted) and a private methodology (the teacher’s own developments, methodological and pedagogical conclusions reflected in the teacher’s scientific articles).

Based on this division of methods, it is possible to divide teaching methods: into objective teaching methods (these are basic teaching methods and

their classifications, reflected in the scientific research of generally recognized scientific teachers) and subjective (one could call them “private” teaching methods (these are teaching methods , which are created in practical pedagogical activity by the teacher himself or those methods that practical teachers use in their work; objective teaching methods already tested by other teachers, but at the same time add or change the co-holding part of the method at your discretion).

Based on such a variety of interpretations of the concepts of “teaching method” and “teaching methodology”, the division of teaching methods into objective and subjective, it is necessary to consider modern classifications of methods. Classification in science is created according to certain criteria that the teacher defines for himself before starting work, guided by the goals, conditions and objectives of his research or practical pedagogical work. This includes:

- teacher experience;
- planned goals (including educational) and tasks in the learning process;
- specifics of the university;
- psychological, gender and age characteristics of students;
- level of training of students;
- list of competencies identified in the PLO;
- location of the lesson thematically;
- material and technical equipment of the audience, university;
- level of motivation of students;
- type of occupation;
- level of training of students;
- the teacher’s ability to navigate, including cultural phenomena [10];
- features of the techniques used in the lesson, and many other conditions that must be taken into account.

The main modern classifications of methods appeared at the beginning of the 20th century, the main differences being a certain feature. Today, there are several dozen classifications of teaching methods, each of which has the right to life and its application in practical teaching activities. Knowledge of all possible classifications of teaching methods will not give the expected effect for the growth of professionalism of a practicing teacher, especially a beginner. But at the same time, consider

By selectively classifying, they create, especially for young teachers, a certain theoretical basis or basis for developing material for subjective or creative teaching methods in their subsequent teaching activities.

It would be advisable to give the most commonly used and most frequently used classification in practice according to the source of knowledge, in which teaching methods are divided into:

- verbal;
- practical;
- visual.

Today it is advisable to add a video method and a method of working with a book. Speaking about the method of working with the book, let us turn to the opinion of M.V. Lomonosov, who believed that the verbal method of teaching is the leading one, since “the first thing is the word given to him to communicate his thoughts with others” [8]. Although verbal methods do not require detailed theoretical argumentation due to their widespread use throughout the history of pedagogy, it is still necessary to talk about them separately.

Verbal methods provide the foundation of theoretical knowledge (provided that students are ready to “take” this knowledge due to their intellectual preparedness, age characteristics and other conditions in teaching), which will be the basis for working with practical teaching methods. Within the framework of the verbal method, the teacher uses a monologue, story, conversation, a system of questions and answers, analysis of the material, summing up (conclusions).

Verbal methods are classified as traditional, which means there is no innovation (so fashionable today) in them. The teacher’s story and explanations are considered ready-made material that does not arouse the desire in students to independently get to the bottom of the truth.

With all this, verbal methods still remain the leading teaching methods, which continue to help the teacher in educational activities and create conditions for improving the quality of education. In support of this, we can turn to the point of view of Sh. Amonashvili, who believed that the verbal method of teaching is an indicator of the sincerity, professional and sincere interest of the teacher in the result of his work [1].

The verbal method is usually followed by the practical method. Any theoretical material must, on the one hand, be passed through oneself (from the standpoint of psychology and practice). This can be expressed in the analysis of material obtained using the verbal method of teaching, bringing theoretical material into a certain system, using the information received directly in practice, and, finally, it can be both homework (at school) and independent work (at a university). On the other hand, in high school and higher education,

practical methods are used in seminar classes, practical classes and laboratory work.

The visual teaching method, although in our case is third, is most likely the first in terms of its history. Without any education, the ancient man used the visual method, explaining to the younger generation how to get food for themselves, how to protect themselves from wild animals; the first attempts to create writing, and then teaching reading, were always based on the visual method of teaching.

At first glance, especially for a teacher without work experience, this method is simple in itself and, therefore, its application is also unpretentious. In fact, the visual method in the learning process by showing tables, diagrams, and any illustrations on the topic creates conditions for students to engage various types of memory. At the same time, one of the key principles of teaching is implemented - the principle of clarity. The difficulty of using this teaching method is that visibility itself will not achieve the set educational goals if a number of conditions are not taken into account: place and time of demonstration, frequency of demonstration, quality of demonstration, preparedness of the audience (paintings of the Antiquity or Renaissance period with nudes in primary school is unlikely to evoke the feeling of admiration expected by the teacher). For example, one of the founders of pedagogy Y.A. Komensky considered clarity to be an essential element in the learning process [12].

The next teaching method that needs to be briefly described is the method of working with a book or text. Modern technical equipment of education has led to the fact that a book is no longer considered as a kind of beacon of knowledge, it is just a text that can be downloaded to a laptop and worked with there (read, highlight, copy, print). A real teacher at any stage of education should always focus his attention, and especially the attention of students, on books. This can be expressed in a recommended list of literature, in references to a book during explanations, examples from books, working with a textbook in class (even nominally), mandatory reading of specified pages from a book, the electronic version of which is not available due to certain circumstances. Thus, contrary to the emerging opinion that books are completely replaced by electronic analogues, teachers should try to create conditions for students to be interested in the book as a source of knowledge.

The stages of working with a book are taught in elementary school. At each stage of education, these stages are supplemented and become more complex. If

in the first grade it is reading, then in the 5th grade - comprehension, in the 10th grade - analysis, in the first years of university - comparative analysis, then - summarizing material from the book, then in the senior years of the university - a formalized personal point of view on the material read.

Working with a book sharpens attention, arouses interest, improves literacy, forces analysis and comparison, and, undoubtedly, sharpens and improves students' speech. At the same time, the method of working with a book cannot be mandatory; it must come personally from the teacher and be used in the classroom only if the teacher has a personal interest in the book being presented and the students' level of preparation corresponds to the recommended literature.

The next method that I would like to consider in more detail is even an innovative method in a certain sense - the video method. Modern equipment of classrooms in most educational institutions is in itself a condition for the increasingly frequent use of this teaching method in teaching practice. The conditions for using the video method basically coincide with the conditions for using visual methods, but there are also features of its use.

So, the time range of the film should not exceed several minutes, otherwise it will no longer be an activity, but simply watching a video, even if it is documentary content. The content of the film must be reviewed in advance by the teacher until the last minute, so that there is no accident in the lesson. Age characteristics are taken into account when selecting a film library for classes. The video method, unlike the visual one, has a very interesting and necessary feature. So, having a selection of documentaries or feature films, you can, due to emergency circumstances (a teacher gets sick and there is no one to replace him), put on a film and give the task of writing an essay or doing other creative work on the film. Such "manipulation" cannot be carried out with simple static visualization.

Conclusion

Having described several of the most used methods, we note that their use in teaching activities is necessary when using certain conditions that were mentioned in the work. Modern pedagogy and teaching methods use many different types of classifications of teaching methods, thereby forming the theoretical basis of teaching methods, while the teacher, relying on methodological and pedagogical theory, creates through practice his own private teaching methods, introducing into their content the features of the discipline, the features of the future profession students and, of course, their

own personal characteristics, giving these teaching methods a kind of uniqueness in practice and novelty in theory.

Thus, the study of pedagogical and humanitarian disciplines can contribute to:

- development of the creative component of activity;
- to form the moral foundations of the professional activities of specialists;
- to form a civic position and strong beliefs that help ensure the spiritual security of Russian society [2].

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